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Motivating Learners to Learn: Libyan EFL Teachers' Strategies and a Perspective

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ABSTRACT

The pursuit for motivated students, for the teachers who teach, has been analogous to the pursuit of beauty and truth by human kind —the target is worth pursuing but we have only a slender chance of attaining it in our life time. The present study examined the motivational strategies of English language teaching of 85 teachers from different locations in Libya (64 males and 21 females, teaching in a variety of institutional contexts, ranging from secondary schools to universities. The questionnaire data adapted from Dörnyei (1994) were verified by means of reliability analysis. Items, which reduced the internal consistency of a scale, were omitted from the scales and were treated as single-item variables. The frequency items were compared using standardized scores. The data were analyzed by means of frequency, percentage and arithmetic mean. The main findings show that the promoting goal setting and goal-orientedness were rather neglected area in the participating teachers' practice. This tells that the teachers' own behavioural modeling could be exploited more thoroughly in motivating learners. Based on this study's findings, some applicable and useful motivational strategies are recommended for enhancement and improvement of the students' motivation.

Keywords: Motivational strategies, teachers' motivation, students' motivation, behavioural model

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1. Introduction

If a person intends to do something, a motivation is an inclination. It is also a kind of internal process that makes a person reach a destination. Intelligence can directly be observed but motivation can't. The latter can only be inferred by noting a person's deportment. A motivated class is the one every teacher wishes. It is the fact that we believe the benefits of having students who are excited to learning. For the teachers who quest for motivated students, traditionally, it has been analogous to the pursuit of exquisiteness and truth by humankind—the destiny is worth pursuing but we have only a slim opportunity of achieving it in our lifetime. The pleasure in the teaching role is amplified by their strengths and passion. Consequently it provides fuel for the fire of our contribution. Self deportment troubles lower, communication continues, anxiety decreases, and teaching can be the skill that so many of us have been witnessed it. All these are feasible with motivated students. It will be a different experience we get with demotivated students. Self deportment troubles increase, communication is complicated at best, anxiety is heightened and teaching becomes a badgering and nagging chore.

Many pedagogues believe that student motivation in the classroom is very crucial. Hence, it is the topic to be discussed frequently in education. As a result, motivation is designed in terms of possessions like interest and tendency or moulding students' self confidence and self-esteem or rewards or goals. Motivation is an inherent module of effective memory operation and plays a significant role in effective and efficient portion of working memory to learning. Understanding how motivation works, in combination with working memory, will aid teachers comprehend how the various motivational

constructs they have heard about actually work to motivate students to learn (Duane, David, Guy, Kathleen, Douglas, & Lynne, 2010). So motivational ideas are apparently everywhere, and it is currently one of the most researched topics in education. Consequently, motivational techniques or strategies play crucial role to strengthen students' performance and reinforce their positive attitudes towards learning. Hence, the present paper offers concrete ideas about how teachers examine motivational strategies in learning process which can create a milieu that promotes learning (Margery, & Raymond, 2009). It is well-known that the research on motivation is predictable to be valuable for both teachers and learners and because of the innermost importance attached to motivation by practitioners and researchers alike, motivation has been the target of a great deal of research during the past decades. Therefore, the study aimed to explore the use of motivational strategies of English language teaching among the Libyan EFL teachers and to elaborate on the differences in motivation among the Libyan EFL students according to class levels. While doing this, the following research questions guided the study: 1) What is the general tendency of motivation strategies among the research sample? 2) Are there any important differences in motivation among the Libyan EFL learners?

The researcher has assumed that the EFL learners are not motivated to learn English language and there may be significant statistical difference in motivation among the Libyan EFL learners due to their levels.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Defining Motivation

Motivation is a complex concept to separate from other factors, in Meta analysis of motivation studies, but Margaret and Gardner (2003) concluded that "motivation is more highly related to second language

achievement” than other factors. The more the learner sees him or herself as doing well, the more he or she wants to do even better. Perceptions of disappointment demotivate. Errands and resources are motivating factors for these demotivated students in order for them to see their growth (Cheah, 2003) and so presenting productive activities can “make a massive distinction in students’ attitudes toward learning” (Dornyei, 2003).

Motivation is not identical with achievement, and achievement test scores cannot help to measure student motivation. A variety of factors determines instantaneous achievement and test performance and may even assure through a variety of ways, and some practices that serve to add to increase immediate achievement may truly have the result of waning students’ attention in learning as well as their long term attachment in learning. When we, as teachers, discuss about motivation as a chief motto, we are determined with students’ “motivation to learn”. We are concerned with whether students instigate learning activities and maintaining a participation in learning as well as a dedication to the progression of learning if we place a value on developing a motivation to learn in students. Long term quality participation will be sustained and contributed in learning by efficient schools and efficient teachers are those who build up goals, beliefs, and attitudes in students (Carole, 1990).

The reason of why human behaviour occurs is purely dealt with motivation. According to most psychologists and educators, motivation is a word to describe the process which involves:

1. stimulate and initiate conduct
2. provide way and intention to conduct
3. maintain to let conduct to persevere and
4. guide to opting for choosing a meticulous conduct

However, teachers, focus on the following questions, while dealing with the concept of motivation:

1. How are my students helped to get started?
2. What can they be done to keep going? or
3. What should they be done next?

Motivation, as a chronological pattern in learning, frequently takes the following structure:

Energy ⇒ choice ⇒ course ⇒ contribution ⇒ completion (Reymond, 1978).

Dörnyei and Csizér (1998) suggested that there are Ten Commandments that motivate language learner. They are:

1. Put an individual pattern with your own conduct.
2. Generate a pleasing, tranquil mood in the classroom.
3. Present the errands appropriately.
4. Build up a high-quality association with the learners.
5. Boost the learner’s linguistic self-assurance.
6. Create the language classes fascinating.
7. Encourage learner self-sufficiency.
8. Personalise the learning procedure.
9. Enhance the learners’ goal-orientation.
10. Make known learners with the target language culture

2.2 Significance of Motivation

Motivation is described as a kind of factor that reminds one’s self justice to mould the general deportment in order to reach a target goal. This elucidates that motivation inspires an organism to do a certain task. It is also argued that motivation is a basis for an organism to perform some assignment (Dornyei, 1990). People are naturally inquisitive as human behaviour is versatile. Consequently, instructional designers should meet the challenges of designing instruction assisted by motivation, because it is of

paramount significance to student achievement. When students are motivated, they work longer, harder and with more energy than they are not. In fact motivation assists individuals trounce sluggishness. This takes place so for the reason that in the teaching-learning process, as in other various activities, there should be something that drives their mind or dangles in front to make them more vigorous and vibrant, in classroom teaching, the chief assignment is to nurture student curiosity as a motivation for learning. This is significant because curiosity is motivation that is crucial to learning (Dornyei, 1996).

Learning often becomes associated with drudgery instead of pleasure. A large number of students, more than one in four, leaves schools before graduating. Many more are physically present in the classroom but largely mentally absent; they fail to invest themselves fully in the experience of learning. According to behaviourists, the main influence on learning is reward and punishment. It is obvious that behaviour can be determined toward a reward or away from a punishment. So, the involvement or non-involvement of motivation in the classroom situation is more or less a question of a carrot-and-stick approach. This is really a subject of discussion that educators mention to each other on different occasions. The basic question is should the student (the human child) be, like Pavlov's dog, driven/encouraged to a stimulus that dangles in front of him/her? Awareness of how students' attitudes and beliefs about learning develop and what facilitates learning for its own sake can assist educators in reducing student indifference in the direction of learning. Hence, the role and significance of motivation is worth investigation in this regard (Dornyei, 1998).

[2.3 Types of Motivation](#)

The technique or method used to instruct the learners in learning process which attracts the latter ones towards learning is commonly considered as motivational method or strategy. It frequently brings to mind the strategies that are employed to offer incentives for students perform something and or do it with greater intensity if one thinks of the idea of classroom motivation. However, when the teachers study motivation more strictly, they identify that it is not always something that is clubbed to the circumstances (Dornyei, 2000). It can be something that comes from within us. While an absolute distinction can be risky, the teachers might suggest to some motivators as coming from the outside – or being extrinsic, and other coming from within - or being intrinsic. So, the chief methods of motivation in teaching process are classified into two kinds. They are intrinsic motivational strategies and extrinsic motivational strategies.

[2.3.1 Intrinsic Motivation](#)

The motivation which is used to act for the sake of the activity alone is called Intrinsic Motivational Strategy. For instance, if the people wish to write stories intending to enjoy the writing stories, it will be considered as intrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivational forms touch internal sources and that's why they are called so. These forms of motivation may mirror the meeting of a basic need, or can come from an inner source of pleasure such as personal fulfilment (Dornyei, 2001). The teachers will find that there will be substantial long term advantages if they support the development of their students' intrinsic motivation. Students will tend to outperform those who have become habituated to extrinsic reinforcement and incentive if they are with more intrinsic motivational orientation, working within a needs satisfying environment, over time (Dweck, 2000; Glasser, 1986). In Ryan and

Deci (2006) words, intrinsic motivation is “the inherent tendency to engage one’s interests and to exercise and develop one’s capacities.”

It is a comprehensive task to explain intrinsic motivational techniques as separate techniques or strategies when compared to the extrinsic motivational strategies. They, like any other successful methodology, have to be developed purposely, but a holistic approach is most effective. The elimination of barriers to the students’ abilities to access their inner motives and satisfiers is occupied by much of the process of promoting intrinsic motivation. For one’s intrinsic sources of motivation to grow, the learning context must support them. Rewards, pain-based motivators, meaningless tasks, learning in isolation, and a lack of support all these work to block intrinsic sources of motivation (Dornyei, 2003b). To examine many intrinsic motivational ideas within a single structure may be most instructive and practical—that of basic needs. Intrinsic forms are less about adding something, unlike extrinsic forms of motivation (Dornyei, 2005). For example, basic needs merely exist, and we all have them. During the learning process or school day, either they are met within the situation of the learning environment, or students will be forced to meet them in unconventional ways. Students use these alternative ways in some cases to meet their needs manifest as disruptive behaviour and the result will be the problems to the teacher or become the unhealthy habits for the students.

Silent Features of Intrinsic Motivation

It is palpable to figure out the characteristics of intrinsic motivational strategies from the different aspects of the meanings or definitions given by different scholars and educationalists. From the above grounds we can draw the following principles which meet

the basic concept of intrinsic motivational strategy.

- Assumes the learning activity itself gives the satisfaction.
- Flexible to other contexts and situations.
- Takes time to sustain and promote.
- Concentrates chiefly on process based type.
- Entails that the learning/task itself has worth and sense.
- Occurs through natural condition.
- Gives long-lasting advantages.
- Promotes a way of thinking that is useful when transferred into the context of building relationships.
- Promotes ever-increasing levels of self-motivation.
- To rely upon with a fresh group of students who are not familiarized to using these sources of motivation can be complicated.
- Creates the cause-and-effect between responsibility and freedom so that it increases accountable conduct.
- Promotes greater resourcefulness.
- Promotes an importance on process.
- Inspires students’ positive attitude when they solve the problem/reach the goal.
- Allows students to experience inner sources of satisfaction. Activities feel inherently meaningful and as though they are “going somewhere” psychologically; as a result there is little experience of monotony.
- Promotes student creativity and sets the stage for communal bonds among students.
- Gets people engaged for no reward other than the curiosity and pleasure that accompanies them.
- Relates goals to learners’ self esteem.

- Individual factors are individual in the sense that they function even when a student is working alone.
- Attracts the learner's attention
- Stimulates sensory curiosity by creating abrupt changes that will be professed by the senses.
- Stimulates cognitive curiosity by making a person wonder about something.
- Enables the learners to believe that their effort will lead to powerful effects.
- Admits learners to freely choose what they crave to learn and how they will learn it.
- Gives opportunity to the learners to use mental images of things and situations that are not actually present to stimulate their behaviour. This helps them envisage themselves using the learned information in real- life settings.
- Encourages learners help others to achieve their goals. As a result, the learners are much satisfied. So, it creates a channel to develop interpersonal skills.

Strategies or Techniques of Intrinsic Motivation

There are numerous kinds of intrinsic motivational strategies. The most common strategies found in teaching practice are as follows:

Greater Responsibility: This strategy creates the cause and effect between responsibility and self-determination which ultimately increases students' responsible department.

Problem Solving and Inquiry Based Learning: This can develop superior resourcefulness. It also promotes an importance on process as a result get motivated when the students work out the problem or reach the aim.

Basic Needs Satisfying Environment: This motivational strategy permits the pupils to experience inner sources of satisfaction. The

activities they do give a sense of feeling naturally meaningful and as though they are 'going somewhere' psychologically; as a result there is little experience of monotony. It also improves student creativity and sets the stage for communal bonds among students.

Self Improvement: This kind of strategy encourages to assist the students clarify their own goals and desires. The satisfaction the students get from this technique is long lasting sense of satisfaction.

2.3.2 Extrinsic Motivation

The motivation which is used to act for external rewards is called Extrinsic Motivation. For instance, if the people wish to write stories intending for the hope of getting published, being famous, or making money, it will be considered as extrinsic motivation. Extrinsic motivational forms touch external sources and that's why they are named so. These motivators chiefly come from an external agent, such as a reward from the teacher. Extrinsic motivational strategies include grades, rewards, praise, punishments, public recognition and phone calls home (Dornyei & Ottó, 1998). Brown (2007) says that extrinsic motivation is either tangible or psychological in nature that indicates our tendency to perform activities for external rewards. Here money for instance, indicates tangible and fame indicates psychological aspects. According to Karageorghis and Terry (2010), Extrinsic Motivation focuses external factors such as winning medals, receiving financial rewards, and attracting attention from the media.

Silent Features of Extrinsic Motivational Strategies

It is obvious to figure out the characteristics of extrinsic motivational strategies from the different aspects of the meanings. From the above grounds we can draw the following characteristics which

meet the basic concept of extrinsic motivational strategy.

- Assumes that an extrinsic motivator is essential.
- Not convertible outside the situation that the reward is present.
- Can be relied upon after only a short period of introduction.
- Chiefly product-focused.
- Implies the learning/task is a means to an end (the reward).
- Occurs through artificial condition.
- Gives short-term advantages.
- Promotes a mentality that may hinder the inclination to invest in the relationship-building process.
- Promotes an ever-increasing need for rewards.
- Can be useful to incorporate to motivate a behaviour that is unfamiliar or unformed.
- Tangible, familiar, motivating to students who value them. Similar to monetary motivators in that they work as rewards.
- Can be useful to define valued outcomes or processes. Help clarify the focus of the effort.
- Feels good. Works to make student work harder.
- Works in the short-term. Motivates students who are used to that technique. Can help clarify the boundaries in a class.
- Can reward behaviour and effort that may not be rewarded by peers. Feels good to recipient.
- Can alert parents to patterns of which they may not have been aware. Demonstrates a commitment to the student's success. Positive calls can have a profoundly positive outcome.
- Helps to shape the desired behaviour. Can be done quickly, efficiently and without

much cost or planning. Can provide useful feedback for self-improvement.

Strategies or Techniques of Extrinsic Motivation

Though there are various extrinsic motivational strategies, the most prevalent ones are

Personal Praise: This strategy works in short term. The students feel good when they are praised. This strategy assists the students to work harder.

Incentives: This kind of technique is useful to describe esteemed results or processes. It aids clarify the goal of the endeavour.

Grades and Rewards: This sort of motivational strategy is concrete, well-known. Gives much motivation to the students who value them. This technique is similar to monetary motivators in that they work as rewards.

Public Recognition: It can reward department and attempt that may not be rewarded by peers. The recipient feels good when he or she gets recognition from the public.

2.4 Relevant Research

Wechsumangkalo and Prasertrattanadecho's (2004) study denoted vividly that low English proficiency subjects are less interactively motivated than high English proficiency subjects. However, in the level of instrumental motivation between two groups of subjects there was no significant difference. Moreover, the study demonstrated that low English proficiency subjects with low English achievement are less motivated than high English proficiency subjects.

Hedge (2000) conducted a study which examined the motivation of 20 Japanese students who were studying English. The findings in this research indicated that the most common reasons for studying English

as a second language. These findings focus on

- for interaction with abroad people
- finding work in a high profile career, processing international information and
- understanding other cultures

The study of Gardner and Lambert (1972) was related with these findings which suggested that a person's requirement for studying a second language is for the skill to socialize with the learning language community or integrative motivation and the ability to increase knowledge applied from that learning language or instrumental motivation.

3 Methodology

3.1 Participants

Participants were 85 teachers of English in Libya (64 males and 21 females, teaching in a variety of institutional contexts, ranging from secondary schools to universities; as can be seen in Table 1, many of the participants were teaching in different contexts at the same time, which is a typical feature of English teaching in different institutions in Traghan, Ghat, Obari, Murzuk, Alkhooms, due to greater demand for qualified professionals. In selecting the respondents the researcher aimed to achieve diversity and to this end, the data were collected from different locations in Libya, and the participating teachers also showed wide differences in terms of their teaching experience: 10% had less than five year's experience, 40% had been teaching over ten years, 35 % had been teaching over fifteen years and 15% had been teaching over eighteen years of teaching. In addition, 40% of the sample, 20 of the respondents, were foreign teachers of teaching English in Libya.

Table 1: Types of the participants' (N = 85) teaching context*

Type of context	N	Percentage (%)
University	58	68.24
Secondary school	11	12.94
Private practice	16	18.82

*One teacher may teach in more than one context.

3.2 Instruments

Teachers' experiences about strategy use can be described from the aspect of how frequently they actually used the motivational strategies. In order to cover the aspects, the researcher developed a questionnaire which included the set of motivational strategies, and respondents were asked to rate each strategy on a five-point scale in terms of the *frequency of its use* ('hardly ever' □□□ 'very often') based on the teacher's past experience.

The selection of the strategies to be included in the questionnaire was based on Dörnyei (1994), and a first version was piloted with 25 respondents. As a result of this pilot study, wording was revised in several places, some strategies were omitted from the list, and some new ones that the respondents considered important were added. The final version of the questionnaire contained 50 motivational strategies (see appendix for a complete list) and a few personal questions eliciting background information about the teachers. Because the respondents were teachers of English (and some of them foreigners teaching English in Libya) and the language of the questionnaire was English.

3.3 Data Collection Procedure

The questionnaires were distributed to 85 teachers during their normal class session during which they were given clear directions and elucidation for filling out the questionnaires. The questionnaires were collected upon completion.

4. Data Analysis and Discussion

The questionnaire's data were submitted to a number of statistical examinations. The 50 strategy items were verified by means of reliability analysis. Items which reduced the internal consistency of a scale were omitted from the scales and were treated as single-

item variables. The frequency items were compared using standardized scores. The data were analyzed by means of frequency, percentage and arithmetic mean. (More details about the analyses are provided below.)

4.1 Reliability and Validity

The scale was detected for both reliability and validity as shown on the following table:

Table 2: The Frequency statistics rank scale: relative frequency (z-diff)^a, mean frequency ($\bar{X}$); item's mean frequency's difference from the overall mean frequency of all the items ($\bar{X}$ -diff)

Motivational Strategy	Z - diff	$\bar{X}$	$\bar{X}$ Diff
Q.1	-.32	5.90	.83
Q.2	-.18	5.82	.75
Q.3	-.32	5.90	.83
Q.4	-.14	6.24	1.17
Q.5	.25	6.27	1.20
Q.6	-.58	6.18	1.11
Q.7	-.05	5.37	.30
Q.8	.14	5.65	.58
Q.9	-.05	5.37	.30
Q.10	-.31	4.94	-.13
Q.11	-.14	6.24	1.17
Q.12	-.39	6.04	.97
Q.13	-.08	5.99	.92
Q.14	.21	6.61	1.54
Q.15	-.11	3.67	-1.40
Q.16	.19	5.65	.58
Q.17	-.55	5.07	.00
Q.18	-.31	4.94	-.13
Q.19	-.19	6.30	1.23
Q.20	.25	6.27	1.20
Q.21	-.05	5.37	.30
Q.22	-.31	4.94	-.13
Q.23	-.56	3.14	-1.93
Q.24	.19	6.39	1.32
Q.25	-.13	6.18	1.11
Q.26	-.20	5.95	.88
Q.27	.03	5.89	.82
Q.28	.43	5.46	.39
Q.29	-.46	6.11	1.04
Q.30	-.60	5.55	.48
Q.31	.18	4.18	-.89

Q.32	-.55	5.07	.00
Q.33	-.20	5.95	.88
Q.34	-.55	5.07	.00
Q.35	.18	4.18	-.89
Q.36	-.56	3.14	-1.93
Q.37	-.17	6.01	.94
Q.38	-.39	6.04	.97
Q.39	.05	5.18	.11
Q.40	.44	5.80	.73
Q.41	-.96	2.53	-2.55
Q.42	.19	4.60	-.47
Q.43	.05	5.18	.11
Q.44	.43	5.46	.39
Q.45	.03	5.89	.82
Q.46	-.09	5.86	.79
Q.47	-.09	4.67	-.40
Q.48	-.46	6.11	1.04
Q.49	-.09	4.67	-.40
Q.50	-.11	3.67	-1.40

4.2 Statistical tests used to analyze data

The researcher employed the following statistical tests to verify the research hypotheses:

1. T-test for one sample.
2. One-way analysis of variance.

4.3 Results & Discussion

The result obtained for each hypothesis and its interpretation and discussion are presented here:

4.3.1 Hypothesis 1

It was presumed that learners were not motivated to learn English language. To confirm this hypothesis, the researcher employed T-test for one sample as shown on the following table:

Table 3: Result of (T-test)

		Result of (T-test)					
		95% assurance Interval of the Variation					
	Test Value = 45	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Lower	Upper
motivation	5.558	45	.000	8.30000	5.2797	11.3203	

Table shows that mean variation is important at (.000), which points out that motivation scores are high among the learners.

Discussion

The result reveals that students' motivation for learning English is high. It can

be observed that this result was in line with the results of connected studies conducted worldwide (AlAzoumi, 2014; Nguyen, 2014; Richard, 2006; Vijchulata & Lee, 1985; Shaaban, Ghaith, 2000; Kris & Machiko, 2006). Owing to the learners, ongoing keenness and desire to learn and master English as foreign language was predictable. Now-a-days it is very prevalent that the reputation of English language might be one of the motives why English language learners in various parts of the world are well-motivated to that end. It is fact that students' craving to take part in the learning process is connected with student motivation to learn English in Libya. The reasons that inspire their participation or nonparticipation might also be related to academic activities.

4.3.2 Hypothesis 2

There was significant statistical difference on motivation among English language learner class levels. The researcher employed one-way analysis of variance to examine this hypothesis as shown in the following table:

Table 4: Analysis of Variance

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	831.205	5	166.241	2.009	.130
Within Groups	3310.760	40	82.769		
Total	4141.965	45			

The results in the table above show no significant statistical variance in motivation due to students' class levels.

Discussion

The outcome of this hypothesis indicated no significant statistical variances were found on motivation scores due to student class levels. As per researcher, learners are usually found in classrooms and each learner, regardless of his/her class, is expected to be an active member in learning process. Other factors such as nature of learners, class environment, and extracurricular activities also influence the learners effectively to class motivation to learn English language.

5. Conclusion

The study was aimed at drawing up a set of the most important motivational strategies that language teachers could use to enhance motivation in their classes. In order to provide some experimental finding for the present study as recommended list of strategies, the researcher used data from practicing teachers working in a variety of institutions. These data were interpreted in the light of teachers past experience and the research literature, resulting in the formulation of a set of motivational strategies. These strategies provide as a reassurance about the validity of the present study results, as does the fact that the emerging final set appears to be supported by motivational theory and covers most well-documented dimensions of inspiration.

The researcher's analysis of the frequency of the actual classroom use of the proposed motivational strategies shows that promoting goal setting and goal - orientedness was a rather neglected area in the participating teachers' practice. The data also pointed to the fact that the teachers' own behavioural modeling could be exploited more thoroughly in motivating learners. Some additional subfields where improvements were considered desirable included: creating regular opportunities for students to experience success; making learning activities challenging and thus involving; and giving clearer instructions. Finally, the researcher would like to point out that the present study could offer only a tentative ranking of the various motivational strategies, since teacher beliefs may not coincide with actual strategy effectiveness. My investigation did not involve the testing of the learning benefits of the strategies or their actual frequency, but rather yielded only perceived measures; further research following an experimental design is needed to examine the extent to which the motivational strategies actually work in the

classroom, and to specify the optimal conditions for and constraints of their use.

With regard to what to be done, the best insight the teacher has is that motivated students help motivate teachers, and motivated teachers help motivate students (Dornyei, & Schmidt, 2001). The series usually begin with us because we stand the responsibility as professional educators. It emphasizes that every time we facilitate student motivation to learn, we are directly contributing to our own motivation to teach. Those smiling enthusiastic faces, those moments of insight and wonder, those student expressions of completion and accomplishment, and those heads held upright and eyes wide that say, "I did it; I learned something," are the force, that gives life to our work (Dornyei, Csizer, & Nemeth, 2006). Experience them; they occur in any class. By paying attention to them and savoring them, we affirm our existence. As building the future citizens, teachers cannot ask for them -they can only see them, they can take a look and then plan, organize, and, above all else, enjoy the pleasure of being inspired.

Recommendations

Based on the results, the following things are expected-

1. To encourage students consciousness towards learning process.
2. To bring the awareness of using modern English language teaching techniques among the learners.

To sum up, further investigations are required into various components of motivation at various places in Libya including schools and universities.

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Appendix: Questionnaire on motivational strategies for the Libyan EFL Teachers
Dear Participants,

The researcher is conducting an investigation study on “Motivating Learners to Learn: Libyan EFL Teachers’ Strategies and a Perspective.” The present questionnaire relates to the motivational strategies that you use to motivate your students and ultimately it endeavours to explore the possible sources to inspire the knowledge seekers towards learning. Give pleasure to note that your names will be kept surreptitious and so be candid and sincere in giving facts or opinions. The researcher highly appreciates your time and endeavour to contribute in this study, which shows your profound adore for education.

MOTIVATIONAL STRATEGIES

Please specify how frequently you use the following motivational strategies in your class, by giving tick on the appropriate option. Please answer all the questions.

1. Hardly Ever
2. Ever
3. Neither Ever / Often
4. Often
5. Very Often

Sl.No	Strategies	1	2	3	4	5
1.	I show my enthusiasm for teaching					
2.	I encourage creative and imaginative ideas					
3.	I teach my students self-learning strategies					
4.	I help my students to get to know each other					
5.	I encourage my students to give suggestions for improving the course					
6.	Prepare for the lessons properly					
7.	I use activities that familiarize students with the target culture					
8.	I share my personal interests with my students					
9.	I encourage my students to use English outside the classroom					
10.	I set class rules myself rather than allowing my students to do so					
11.	I try to establish a good rapport with my students					
12.	I show a good example by being committed and motivated					
13.	I show my students that I care about them as people					
14.	I am careful to avoid embarrassing my students when giving feedback					
15.	I encourage my students to set specific, learning goals for themselves					
16.	I demystify mistakes which are a natural part of learning.					
17.	I use activities which allow my students to mix					
18.	I highlight and review class learning goals with my students					
19.	I create a supportive classroom environment so my students feel encouraged to take risks					
20.	I ask my students what they like about the course/ learning process					
21.	I encourage students to be realistic about their language learning goals					
22.	I make sure tasks are challenging but possible for my students					
23.	I persuade my students to teach each other					
24.	I use humour in my classroom					
25.	I give immediate feedback to my students					

26.	I reward my students when they succeed					
27.	I start all my lessons with the same presentation technique					
28.	I use tasks that are well below my students' ability					
29.	I explain the importance of class rules to my students					
30.	I show my students how much they have progressed or learnt					
31.	I explain why a task is meaningful or relevant					
32.	I use tasks that allow my students to interact with each other					
33.	I encourage my students to assess themselves					
34.	I teach my students how to use self-motivating strategies					
35.	I remind my students of the benefits of learning language					
36.	I use a short opening activity to relax and help my students to focus					
37.	I avoid using authentic cultural material which is not from the course book					
38.	I tell my students that they can learn if they make the necessary effort					
39.	I tell my students that communicating meaning effectively, is more important than grammatical accuracy					
40.	I use authentic tasks to prepare my students for real life situations					
41.	I invite former/senior students to share their learning experiences					
42.	I make tasks attractive by using games and competitions					
43.	I match tasks to my students' needs/ interests rather than exam requirements					
44.	I select tasks that do not exceed the learners' competence					
45.	I select tasks from the course book even if they do not relate to students' real life experiences					
46.	I offer a variety of tasks to my students					
47.	I investigate my students learning needs					
48.	I give clear instructions for tasks by modelling					
49.	I do a needs analysis about the learners' language goals and needs					
50.	I involve students in creating their own classroom rules					

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